

Effect of dielectric constant of medium on conductance for acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in normal and branched alcohols

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Abstract : The conductance parameters, Λ_0 (equivalent conductance at infinite dilution) and K_A (association constant) for acetylcholine chloride, bromide, iodide and perchlorate in methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, 2-propanol and *n*-butanol have been evaluated at 25 °C from the conductance measurements.

The values of Λ_0 for different salts decrease with decreasing dielectric constant of medium (*D*) with some variations and are in the order of MeOH > EtOH > 2-PrOH > *n*-PrOH > *n*-BuOH. The association constants of the same salts in different alcohols increase with decreasing dielectric constant of medium and are in the order of *n*-BuOH > 2-PrOH > *n*-PrOH > EtOH > MeOH.

Keywords : Conductance measurement, acetylcholine halides, perchlorate.

Introduction

Recent theories of the behaviour of electrolytes in solution suggest that the dielectric constant of the medium plays a very important role. Debye and Pauling¹ discussed the various factors that influence the dielectric constant of the medium in the immediate neighbourhood of the ion. It was found that in very dilute solutions the dielectric constant of the pure solvent is the proper value to be used for the so-called "Limiting Law". Furthermore, it has been shown that changes of dielectric constant of the medium are closely connected with the corresponding changes of the velocity of homogeneous reactions in solutions. An approach to a theoretical interpretation of the relation of these medium changes to the simultaneous changes in the velocity of certain catalyzed reactions was given by Hamed and Samaras².

The measurement of dielectric constant³ of the conducting solutions is still very much a matter of controversy and definite, reliable results are yet to be obtained. On the other hand, the measurement of the dielectric constant of a pure non-conducting solvent does not offer any particular difficulty and may be carried out by different methods. However, even the purest solvent exhibits some conductivity, and the reliability of measurements decreases rapidly with increasing conductance. Many solvents may act as very weak acids or bases, showing considerable increase of their dissociation constant with increasing tem-

perature and thus also giving less reliable data for their dielectric constant.

Electrolytes in the primary alcohols^{4,5} and amides⁶ appear to exhibit many of the properties previously observed only in water^{7,8} and were attributed to the unique structure of that solvent. In alcohols, ionic association was found to increase with anionic size, a result contrary to the predictions of the electrostatic theory. This was interpreted in terms of a multiple-step association process involving hydrogen bonded solvation of anions in the homologous series methanol to 1-pentanol.

Results and discussion

It can be readily seen from Table 1 that the equivalent conductances at infinite dilution (Λ_0) of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate decrease with decreasing dielectric constant of medium with some variations and are in the order of MeOH > EtOH > 2-PrOH > *n*-PrOH > *n*-BuOH.

The association constants of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate increase with decreasing dielectric constant of medium and are in the order of *n*-BuOH > 2-PrOH > *n*-PrOH > EtOH > MeOH. It also increases with increasing anionic size in each case following the order of ClO₄ > I > Br > Cl. The prediction of electrostatic theory that the association of an electrolyte in a solvent containing hydroxy groups appears to increase with ionic

size. An analysis of the concentration dependence of conductance in methanol solutions gives association constants for alkali metal and tetra-alkylammonium halides which increase as the size of the anion increases¹⁴. For example, constants of 0, 4 and 18 have been obtained for tetra-alkylammonium chloride, bromide, and iodide, respectively⁴.

Recent studies of Kay and co-workers on the conductivity of several alkylammonium halides in methanol and ethanol^{4,14} have clearly supported our findings concerning the influence of solvent on the association of ion-pairs. Hafez *et al.*¹⁵ found that Λ_o for *s-n*-alkylisothiuronium bromides, iodides and picrates in ethanol, *n*-propanol and *n*-butanol decreases while K_A increases with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium.

El-Hammamy *et al.*¹⁶ found similar behaviour for Λ_o and K_A values of *N,N*-diphenyl-*s-n*-alkylisothiuronium bromides in methanol, ethanol and *n*-propanol. The decrease of Λ_o is attributed to decrease in ion mobility as the dielectric constant decreases, while the increase of K_A may be due to the increase of the number of non-conducting ion-pairs under such condition of decreased mobility.

The effect of solvent is two fold : (a) it can stabilize the ion-pairs due to the hydrogen bond chains in the alcohol, (b) it can solvate anions by hydrogen bonding¹⁷ so that the K_A values increase.

The participation of alcohols in the ion-pair formation equilibrium, therefore, should involve both steric effect and coulombic effect. On the basis of this approach the

structural modifications of the alcoholic polymers generated by added solvents should result in a variable influence of the alcohol molecules on the ion-pair association of electrolytes.

When the higher alcohols are chosen as the solvent system, the pattern of ionic association of hydroxy solvents may be investigated without such complications as three-dimensional structural effects or small association constant⁴. Consequently, the K_A values in mixed solvents should vary with the mixture composition in a way different from that expected on the basis of the short range ion-ion interactions which depend only on the dielectric constant of the solvent.

The association constant should be only a function of the dielectric constant, their values increase with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. This is found to be true in studying the behaviour of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, 2-propanol and *n*-butanol. The association constant was also generally found to increase with increasing anionic size in each alcohol as in Table 1. The same behaviour of Λ_o and K_A was obtained for tetrabutylammonium halides and perchlorate in different alcohols at 25 °C^{4,14} and is illustrated in Table 2.

From the above picture of the variation of both Λ_o and K_A with dielectric constant of alcohols, one may conclude that the sphere in continuum model cannot be applied to these systems. Kay and his co-workers¹⁴ studied some salts of the tetra-alkylammonium in methyl alcohol. They obtained values of K_A higher than those expected

Table 1. Λ_o and K_A values in different alcohols at 25 °C⁹⁻¹³

Salt	$D = 32.63$		$D = 24.33$		$D = 20.33$		$D = 19.41$		$D = 17.51$	
	Methanol		Ethanol		<i>n</i> -Propanol		2-Propanol		<i>n</i> -Butanol	
	Λ_o	K_A	Λ_o	K_A	Λ_o	K_A	Λ_o	K_A	Λ_o	K_A
Acetylcholine Cl ⁻	97.03	11.63	42.05	61.50	20.51	174.48	22.89	460.37	14.05	1177.90
Acetylcholine Br ⁻	100.98	27.38	44.60	65.46	22.36	194.68	23.35	670.03	14.81	1188.20
Acetylcholine I ⁻	107.09	18.79	47.37	56.87	23.87	361.81	24.41	935.50	15.04	1137.30
Acetylcholine ClO ₄ ⁻	114.42	36.23	52.05	106.32	27.19	765.76	27.93	1051.80	18.24	2863.00

Table 2. Λ_o and K_A values in different alcohols at 25 °C for tetrabutylammonium halides and perchlorate^{4,14}

Salt	Methanol		Ethanol		<i>n</i> -Propanol	
	Λ_o	K_A	Λ_o	K_A	Λ_o	K_A
Bu ₄ NCl	91.38	0	41.54	39	12.16	149
Bu ₄ NBr	95.37	2.6	43.31	75	22.92	266
Bu ₄ NI	101.72	15.6	46.56	123	24.60	415
Bu ₄ NClO ₄	-	-	-	-	27.13	769

by using the Bjerrum-Fross theory¹⁸. They explained their results on the hypothesis that the ion-pair association is affected by the particular structure of the alcohol.

It can be readily seen from Table 3^{19,20} that, the association constant increases with increasing cation size, in the order of CsI > RbI > KI > NaI. This can be ex-

plained by adopting the Lee and Wheaton^{20,21} assumption namely, the formation of solvent-separated-ion pairs. Lee and Wheaton^{19,20} obtained a similar behaviour for alkali iodides in different alcohols. Fig. 1 shows the plot of $\log K_A$ vs $1/D$, which is linear as expected from the relation²¹ :

$$\log K_A = \log K_A^0 + e^2/a^0 DKT$$

Accasina *et al.*²² studied the conductance of LiClO_4 in dioxane-water mixtures at 25 °C and found a slight curvature and Hafez *et al.*¹⁵ measured the conductance of *s-n*-alkylisothiuronium bromides, iodides and picrates in ethanol, *n*-propanol and *n*-butanol. They found that in most cases straight lines were obtained according to ionic association equation²². In other cases a slight curvature was due to the interference of ion-solvent interaction²³.

El-Hammamy *et al.*¹⁶ measured the conductance of *N,N'*-diphenyl-*s-n*-alkylisothiuronium bromides in methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol and *n*-butanol. They found a curvature in the same plot. This behaviour was explained as being due to solute-solvent interaction.

El-Hammamy and Ahmed²⁴ measured the conductance of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in methanol, ethanol and *n*-propanol and found straight lines according to ionic association equation²².

Fig. 1. Variation of $\log K_A$ vs $1/D$ for acetylcholine-chloride, -bromide, -iodide and -perchlorate at 25 °C.

Experimental

The acetylcholine chloride, bromide, iodide and perchlorate were purified as reported in the literature⁹⁻¹³. Methanol (B.D.H.), ethanol (B.D.H.), *n*-propanol (Cambrian Chemical), 2-propanol (Cambrian Chemical) and

Table 3. Conductance data for some alkali metal salts at 25 °C^{19,20}

Salt	Methanol		Ethanol		<i>n</i> -Propanol	
	Λ_o	K_A	Λ_o	K_A	Λ_o	K_A
NaI	108.51	12.8	47.57	55.8	24.38	191.9
KI	115.51	13.2	50.70	81.9	26.31	350.2
RbI	119.68	18.0	52.18	105.4	26.99	472.0
CsI	124.22	23.1	53.63	140.5	27.72	646.4

Table 4. Solvents properties at 25 °C

Solvent	Density (d) (g cm^{-3})	Viscosity (η) (poise)	Specific conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)
MeOH	0.78657	0.5448×10^{-2}	$1.6-3.9 \times 10^{-7}$
EtOH	0.78511	1.0840×10^{-2}	$5.4-9 \times 10^{-8}$
<i>n</i> -PrOH	0.79960	1.9520×10^{-2}	$2.3-4.8 \times 10^{-8}$
2-PrOH	0.78097	2.0790×10^{-2}	5.443×10^{-8}
<i>n</i> -BuOH	0.80572	2.5890×10^{-2}	3.810×10^{-8}

n-butanol (B.D.H.) were purified as a previously reported⁹⁻¹³.

The densities (*d*) of the alcohols were determined using a 20 ml pycnometer at 25 ± 0.02 °C (Table 4). The viscosities (η) were measured using a modified Ubelohde suspended level viscometer with flow time at 25 °C of 172.4 s for conductivity water (Table 4). The values of the dielectric constants used were literature values⁹⁻¹³. An Erlenmeyer conductivity cell with unplatinized electrodes was used conductivity measurements. The cell constant ($0.05443 \pm 0.43\%$) was determined using the Lind, Zwolenik and Fuoss equation²⁵.

A "Pye" 11700 conductance bridge was used for measuring the resistance of solution at 5 Kc/s.

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